

Vol.13 No4 (III)

ISSN : 0975-1386

Wesleyan Journal of Research

An International Research Journal

SCIENCE SECTION

Bankura Christian College
Bankura-722 101
WEST BENGAL, INDIA

UTILIZATION AND CONSUMPTION PATTERN OF IRRIGATION WATER OF HISAR DISTRICT, HARYANA: A BLOCK WISE ANALYSIS.

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ABSTRACT

Water resource is the main base of human's life and it does play a major role for sustainable development of the people, belonged to different strata of society. Keeping in view the growing demand for fresh drinking water, it becomes imperative to make the use of the water resources in a judicious way, so that every segment of the society may get their due share of this natural resource. The present paper examines the irrigation water consumption pattern of the Hisar district of Haryana. The study is based on secondary source of data, gathered from ground water cell Hisar. The block wise study on utilization pattern of irrigation water resources shows a significant regional variability in the water resources consumption pattern in the district Hisar. The findings of the study indicate the block wise disparity and suggest some recommendation.

Keywords: Water resources, consumption pattern, secondary data, cause-effect relationship, regional disparity.

INTRODUCTION:

In India, particularly in the Haryana state in the northwestern parts, groundwater is the main water source supply for domestic, agriculture, industrial consumption. During the recent years, the dependency on the groundwater has raised sharply over the state. It is because of rapid expansion of land use under the rice-wheat crop combination dominance in the state. In Haryana, there was to compute the magnitudes of groundwater level trends and abrupt transforming the point detection's in term of area. There are few studies, carried out on the water resource consumption pattern indicates that there has been considerable diversification in water consumption, taken place during different successive periods.

Intensive irrigation system has given rise to major consumption of ground water resources, particularly in Punjab and Haryana. It is because of assured irrigation, and pioneer areas of green revolution, as a result, the extraction of ground water for mechanized agriculture has significantly risen during different successive periods. There is a study on Bist Doab region of Punjab, India. This study carried out on these areas shows that the spatial pattern of changes in ground water irrigated areas in the Bist Doab areas of Punjab during the 1998-2011 period. Using spatial interpolation, the ground water irrigated areas increased to a consideration extent in the entire region for each year. Spatial data on the intensity of irrigation and the density of tube-well irrigated areas were also analyzed the trend. The results shows that the emergence of a zoning of areas increased by the ground water in the south western part of the Bist Doab. Using these results, we classified the Bist Doab region into three zones (Zone 1, 2, and 3) for prioritizing ground initiatives of the water management in accordance with consumption of ground water for the agricultural purposes. While the consumption of the ground water provides one possible explanation for decreasing the levels of the ground water in the area, other non-anthropogenic factors have also been playing a significant role in such trends. Further research at the same scale is recommended in other parts of the Punjab State (Ranbir & Dhiyan Kaur, 2017) The success of crops is an arid and semi-arid region depends on irrigation, so irrigation has a high priority among the various uses of water. In the absence of sufficient rainfall and semi-arid climate conditions, water availability and control becomes mandatory (Singh, 1998).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The study is aimed at some of the objectives which are as follows:

- To examine the block-wise consumption of irrigation water in Hisar district;
- To recommend some of suggestions to make judicious use of irrigation water.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

In order to analysis the source wise irrigation water in the Hisar district, the secondary source of irrigation has been applied to get the desired results. For this purpose, the data on various irrigation sources, ground water cell records have been collected. As a secondary source of information, other secondary sources were used as government reports, reports of seminars and the conferences, held at different levels. The data has been worked out with the help of Micro Soft-Excel Software has been used for analyse the quantitative data, undertaken for the study. After collecting the secondary data on irrigation water from different sources; the data has been interrelated in a systematic way. In order to show the share of the water; which is utilized as different source of irrigation is shown by Pie-diagram and other cartographic techniques have been used for reveal the various worked out parameters.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

There are numerous of pressing problems associated with water management. Out of numerous of the problem, there has been problem relating to demand and supply of water, so that everyone may get their due share of fresh water for their daily consumption. It is therefore; it becomes imperative to have a periodic review of consumption level of the households, belonged various strata of society. In this context, the present study is an attempt which is expected to throw an adequate light on the consumption pattern at a village level, so that an inference may be drawn on regional variability at block level in Hisar district of Haryana.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The percentages of net sown area to net irrigated area in the district showed a fluctuation over time. The ratio was 60.8 per cent in 1974-75 but increased to 90.1 per cent in 2017-18 (State Statistical Abstract of Haryana, 1974-75 and 2017-18). This increase was due to increase in over-dependence of ground water and good quality of ground water in the area. The number of tube-wells were 13831 in 1974-75 but increased to 75000 tube-wells in 2017-18. At the same time, the area irrigated by Government canals has decreased from 330 000'ha to 206 000'ha in 2017-18. But in 2017-18, the percentage of net irrigated area to net sown area has increased to 29.3 per cent. However, this increase is not so much as a result of an increase in net area under irrigation but an increase in the net area sown. The above mentioned changes have caused variations in cropping pattern also.

Table: 1: Hisar District: Area (%) Under Various Crops to Total Cropped Area

Crops	Years					
	1974-75	1984-85	1994-95	2004-05	2014-15	2018-19
Rice	1.51	3.93	6.78	6.48	7.85	10.86
Jowar	0.9	0.43	0.12	-	-	-
Bajra	7.18	6.41	3.32	5.89	2.44	2.93
Wheat	23.25	32.21	36.22	40.06	39.44	39.13
Barely	2.64	0.72	1.23	1.17	0.69	-
Gram	20.10	8.89	2.58	0.58	-	0.34
Sugarcane	1.51	0.72	0.49	0.98	0.17	-
Cotton	23.06	26.82	31.19	27.89	24.78	22.41
Oil seeds	17.58	17.78	17.26	15.12	23.38	22.24

Source: Calculated form Statistical Abstract of Hisar District, Haryana for the years 1974-75, 1984-85, 1994-95, 2004-05, 2014-15 and 2018-19.

Today, the main crops grown in this region are rice, wheat, sugarcane, cotton, mustard and millet. These crops are irrigated by tube-wells and canals. The reason for the changing structure can be seen in the availability of canal irrigation in the area. It has been observed that the area under water-intensive crops has increased significantly while the area under low-water intensive crops (dry crops) has shown a decreasing trend.

Rice accounted for only 1.51 per cent of the total crop in 1974-75 but by 2018-19, its share 10.86 per cent of the total cropped area.. However, due to excessive demand for water, the problem of water logging has come to the fore, especially along the banks of canals. On the other hand, farmers who grow rice away from the canals use ground water for irrigation on a very large scale resulting in a decrease in water level. Wheat has dominated the cropping of the area since the beginning. But, during 2004-05 to 2018-19, there has been no significant increase in the percentage of wheat area in the total cropped area. It registered a slight decrease from 40.06 per cent of the total cropped area in 2004-05 to 39.13 per cent in 2018-19.

The area of oilseeds increased from 15.58 during the 1974-75 to 22.24 per cent in 2018-19. In contrast, during the same period percentage of area of gram declined from 20.10 per cent to 0.34 per cent. During this time, the area of sugarcane and barely also decreased. The area of cotton as a total cropped area has decreased by 31.19 per cent in 2004-05 to 22.41 per cent in 2018-19. Whereas, the area under sugarcane has come down from 0.51 per cent in 1974-75 to nil in 2018-19. This area has turned into wheat and rice due to canal and tube-well irrigation.

Thus, it is clear that the priority of crops depends upon the availability of water for irrigation the availability of canal irrigation and boring of tube-wells has encouraged rice cultivation in the district. It has also caused water leakage and salinity problems. Inadequate quantity and poor quality of water for irrigation has discouraged farmers from growing many crops like gram and sugarcane.

Irrigation is an integral part of the agronomic practices in Haryana, particularly in Hisar district, where an assured irrigation system has been proved for sustainable agricultural development. In the Hisar district, there are two main source of irrigation. These two main sources are ground water and the canal irrigation. The present study is an attempt which shows a regional variability in the percentage of area irrigated and an area to total geographical area of the district in on one hand. On the other hand, the block wise net irrigated area to net sown areas. The block wise irrigated area to total area and irrigated area to sown area is tabulated as follows:

Table: 2: Block wise Irrigated Area to Total Area and Irrigated Area to Sown Area in Hisar District, Haryana

Blocks	Area (%) Block Irrigated area to Total geographical area of district	Area (%) Block-wise: Net Irrigated area to Net sown area
Adampur	6.05	77.71
Agroha	6.08	82.13
Barwala	10.49	90.42
Hansi-I	13.16	92.63
Hansi-II	6.84	98.27
Hisar-I	8.55	77.29
Hisar-II	12.50	77.99
Narnuand	8.80	93.60
Uklana	5.09	95.69

Source: Calculated from District Census Handbook Hisar 2011

Keeping in view the tabulated data, it has been observed that there was 86 per cent of net area sown under irrigated (Agriculture Department Record, Haryana) in the year 2011. Percentage of net irrigated area from net sown area in Hansi-II and Uklana blocks more than 95 per cent; about 93 per cent in Narnaund block, 92 per cent in Hansi-I block, 90 per cent in Barwala block, 82 per cent in Agroha block, about 77 per cent in Hisar-I, Hisar-II and Adampur blocks in the district. About 64 percent of the area's surface water is irrigated mainly by canals (State Statistical Abstract of Haryana, 2017-18). The irrigation by the canal irrigation system accounts for 95 per cent, total

irrigated area in Adampur, Agroha, Barwala, Hansi-II and Uklana blocks. 36 per cent of the total irrigated area in the study area is irrigated by groundwater structures; wells and Tube-wells (State Statistical Abstract of Haryana, 2017-18). More than one-third of the total area irrigated by tube-wells is located in Hansi-I, Hisar-I and Hisar-II blocks. Thus, although both surface and groundwater sources are used for irrigation, the limited availability of canal water and its limited periodicity impose a limit on the use of the source. A block-wise assessment of the use of surface and groundwater sources based on 2011 data as follows:

Table: 3 Block-wise Area Irrigated in Accordance with Different Sources in Hisar District, Haryana, 2011

Blocks	Canals	Tube-well/wells	Total Irrigated Area (In hactares)
Adampur	23752 (95.88)	1021 (4.12)	24773 (100)
Agroha	23872 (99.45)	130 (0.55)	24002 (100)
Barwala	41380 (100)	-	41380 (100)
Hansi-I	28968 (55.78)	22961 (44.22)	51929 (100)
Hansi-II	26520 (98.30)	458 (1.70)	26978 (100)
Hisar-I	23317 (69.11)	10419 (30.09)	33736 (100)
Hisar-II	32566 (66.02)	16756 (33.98)	49322 (100)
Narnaund	30766 (88.62)	3948 (11.38)	34714 (100)
Uklana	19959 (99.33)	133 (0.67)	20092 (100)

Source: Calculated from District Census Handbook Hisar 2011.

Adampur Block:

Of the total irrigated area in this block, first 77 per cent irrigate. The wells and tube-wells are also used in the block which is about 4.2 per cent of the total irrigated area. 4 lined canals and 13 unlined canals are available for irrigation in the block. This is clearly shows the importance of surface water in the block. Canal water is available, except KutiaKheri village in the block. The use of wells and tube-wells for irrigation is limited to Karber and Siswal villages. Irrigation from tube-wells is common in blocks except in the villages of Arswan, Bagla, Chudhriwali, Gurshal, Khempur and Mahalsara. Only 1021 hectares area is irrigated from wells and tube-wells in the block. About 45 per cent area of Karber village is irrigated by tube-wells in the block.

Agroha Block:

The canals are the most important source of irrigation accounting for about 99 per cent of the total irrigated area. About 23 lined canals irrigate the block. In most of villages except RisaluKhera village, used canal water for irrigation. Only 130 hectares area irrigated wells/tube-wells. Maximum use of groundwater for irrigation is used by Kalirawan and Agroha Rural villages in the block. Most of villages access canal water for irrigation except, Fransi and KhasaMahajanan villages. The

villages Kirara, Sandol, Shamsukh and Thaska using only canal water for irrigation. Canals are prominent in whole block; it is a primary source for irrigation.

Barwala Block:

In this block a total of 100 per cent area is irrigated by canals. There is 22 lined canals for irrigation. Most villages of this block is irrigated by canal except; KheriBarki, Dhingtana, Sulkhani and Panhari. These villages are not covered by canals. Well/tube-wells irrigation is not available due to deteriorating quality of groundwater. Canals are only the source of irrigation in the block.

Hansi-I Block:

Canal irrigation is not as much prominent in this block. About 44 per cent of total irrigated area in block irrigated by tube-wells. Canals account 56 per cent. About 28 lined canals area available for irrigation in the block. Canals water is available to each village except Depal village in the block. The villages BirHansi, Jamwari, Kajal, Kharkhara, KheriBarkesh and Sisai Bola using only canal water. Hansi Rural, Sultanpur, Mazapur, Puthi, Hajampur, KheriGangan, Sheikhpura, Dhamian, Dhanderi, Ramyan, Depal, Kutubpur, SingwaRagho, Channot, Gurana and Khanpur villages in this block depend entirely on tube-wells. It clearly shows that the importance of groundwater for irrigation in the block.

Hansi-II Block:

There is 98 per cent area in this block is depend on canals for irrigation. About 17 lined canals are available for irrigation. Canals are available to each village except KheraRangran village in this block. Only 1.70 per cent area is irrigated through tube-wells. This area is limited to KheraRangran village. There is total 457 hectares area of these villages irrigated through only tube-wells. It is therefore, the canal system is the main source of irrigation in the block and tube-wells are not prominent source in the block.

Hisar-I Block:

Both the canals and ground water is important source for irrigation in the block. About 69 per cent of total irrigated area in the block is irrigated by canals. A total of 22 lined canals are available for irrigation. Canals are not available in MangaliSurtia, MangaliMohbat, Charnaund and Chiraud villages in these blocks. These villages totally depend on ground water for their irrigation needs. Tube-wells are used in every village except Harikot and Raipur villages in the block.

Hisar-II Block:

Of the total irrigated area in this block, about 78 per cent is irrigated. Canals accounts 66 per cent area irrigates. 26 lined canals are available for irrigation in this block. Both the canals and tube-wells are important sources for irrigation. Canals are not available in Bherian, BhiwaniRuhelan, Chudhriwas, Dhiranwas, GawarGorchi, Kaluwas, PniharChak, Rawalwas, Kirtan, Sarsana and Singhran villages in this block. These villages completed their irrigation demand through tube-wells only. Of the total irrigated area in this block, about 34 per cent is irrigated by tube-wells. Only three villages; Hisar Rural, Nathwan and Tokas are not used tube-wells for irrigation.

Narnund Block:

Canals accounts 88 per cent of the total irrigated area in this block. About 16 lined canals are available for irrigation in this block. Gandas and Rajpura villages is not covered by canals. Both of villages depend on ground water for irrigation. Tube-wells are also an important source for irrigation. Tube-wells account 11 per cent of total irrigated area of the block. Tube-wells used in every village of this block except, KothKhurd, Madha and Luhari Ragho villages because of deteriorating quality of ground water in these villages.

Uklana Block:

Canals account for about 99 per cent of total irrigated area in this block. Only 1 per cent of the area is irrigated by tube-wells. All villages of this block is covered by canal network. Only 131 hectares area is irrigated by tube-wells that are limited to Bithmara and Uklana rural villages. Canals are the only source of irrigation in BhairiAkbarpur and KallarBhaini villages in Uklana block. Canals are the prominent source of irrigation in this block. Thus, it is clear that water for irrigation in the district is provided by both surface and ground water sources. Both are equally important in the district.

However, surface water for irrigation dominate in Adampur, Agroha, Barwala, Hansi-II and Narnuand and Uklana blocks while Hansi-I, Hisar-I and Hisar-II blocks, the dependence of ground water source is high. Ground water is also important in Narnuand block but surface water for irrigation contributes a large part. Hence, any complication in canal water supply or depleting in water level with poor quality has a direct impact on agriculture.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- There should be a judicious use of water, so that every farmer may receive his due share in accordance with the prevailing local conditions;
- There should be a AusraBandi system should be adopted by the each and every farmers belong to each and every village;
- There should be a equilibrium between demand and supply of the irrigation water so that the irrigation water may be utilized in a best way;
- The consumption pattern of irrigation should be evaluated from time to time so that the exploitation of water resources may be compensated accordingly.
- Over exploitation of ground water should be avoided and should be recharged periodically.

CONCLUSION:

Block wise study on area irrigated in accordance with different sources in Hisar district shows a regional variability in the consumption pattern as indicated by the irrigation intensity. The study is based on secondary source of irrigation; which reveals a significant regional disparity, as revealed by the study on villages, belonged to nine blocks of Hisar district of Haryana. Further, the micro level study at village level shows also give the specific findings also indicate the cultivated land; belonged to particular village is dominated by specific mode of irrigation. However, the study show that a particular village, belonged to particular block is irrigated with specific mode of irrigation. It has been observed from the study which shows that the dominancy of irrigation as main source of irrigation ranged from 60 to 70 per cent. In some of the exceptional cases, this irrigation per cent goes up to even 99 per cent in some of the villages of the block Uklana. Where there the ground water is not fit for irrigation, the canal mode of irrigation system is practiced by the farmers. In the absence availability of adequate canal irrigation system, the dry land farming is practiced by the farmers.

Lastly, in order to make use of the ground water in a best ways, as a result, there are some of preventive measures which have been recommended for making judicious use of water, so that a sustainable position may be attained for each and every farmers.

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